

Shifts in Consumer Behavior Due to Corona Pandemic: A Case of Tourism and Hospitality Sector in Bangladesh

Nishat Nigar & Md. Rukon Miah

Abstract:

The study objective is to examine the shifts in consumer behavior during corona pandemic in tourism and hospitality sector in Bangladesh. Convenience type non-probability sampling is used in this research paper and sample size is 150 which are collected from students, teachers and service holders in Dhaka, and Cumilla district area. Descriptive statistics, five rating likert scale and paired sample t-test applied in this research paper to collect data and a focus group including 12 respondents is also created for gathering respondent's opinions about the effect of corona pandemic on restaurants, transportations, hotels and motels. In light of research analysis this research finds that there is a shift in consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality sector due to corona pandemic. Home quarantine, lockdown, physical stress, government rules and regulations have immense impact on consumer's income, consumption, visiting tourist spot due to COVID-19. The study also discloses that consumers are using mask in public places and they are not preferring to purchase foods from restaurant. The findings of this paper may help tourism and hospitality industry to overcome any current and also future pandemic situation. The study also discloses practical guidelines for the tourist, passengers, travelers, restaurants customers and owners and travel agencies to formulate progress of tactical decisions in any pandemic situations. This research might illustrates a frontier study, analytically investigate the potential impacts of COVID-19 on shifts in consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality sector in Bangladesh and how the tourism and hospitality sector may respond to such shifts in the future.

IJSB
Accepted 14 November 2020
Published 20 November 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4282021

Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Tourism and Hospitality Sector, Corona Pandemic, Lockdown, Paired Samples T-Test.

About Author (s)

Nishat Nigar, MBA, University of Rajshahi, **Lecturer**, Department of Marketing, Comilla University, Cumilla, Bangladesh. Email: nishatmkt09@gmail.com

Md. Rukon Miah (corresponding author), BBA student, Department of Marketing, Comilla University, Cumilla, Bangladesh. Email: rukon.mkt10@gmail.com

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Novel coronavirus has driven to an embodied palliation in different types of financial performance in all over the world. The first patient of COVID-19 was indicated in December at Wuhan China and rapidly corona virus was spread in globe. World Health Organization (WHO) pronounced that coronavirus is a pandemic. This pandemic situation has caused voluminous lockdowns in all forms of economic activities. The first corona virus infected people detected in March, 2020 in Bangladesh. To reduce the prevalence of corona pandemic, Government of Bangladesh and all countries in the world have levy lockdowns and also restricted the movement of all tourists nationally and internationally. In Bangladesh all economic activities are changed and moving to owe lockdown slowly in all types of travel and tourism events after Mid-March of 2020. Tourism and hospitality sector is badly affected by pandemic. Hotel, motel, restaurant as well as transport system adjourn because of lockdown throughout the country.

COVID-19 pandemic has influenced consumer behavior in service sector globally, specially the consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality sector. In Bangladesh, We have 12-15 international chain five- star hotels. And also we have many two and three star rated hotels and motels. Tourism and hospitality researchers argued that if lockdown situation will stay long then Bangladesh will face unrecoverable financial losses. Researcher predicted that half a million of employee and employer losing their jobs, who were engaged in the hotel, motel, transportation and restaurant industry. Tourists are not visiting in the tourist destination because of corona pandemic for the fear of getting infected. Biman Bangladesh airlines annulment all of their flights during corona pandemic for that reason they are facing a huge losses. Tourism industry is going to face a huge disaster and also this situation will be continued until corona pandemic situation become normal.

The broad objective of the study is shifts in consumer behavior during corona pandemic: A case of services sector in Bangladesh. Specific objectives in line with the broad objectives are to identify the shifts of consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality due to corona pandemic and to identify the changes of tourists and passenger's behavior (income, consumption, traveling during corona pandemic).

The corona virus has significantly affected Global travel and tourism industry. The Corona virus inbound and outbound effect in Bangladesh and tourists have canceled their hotel and motel booking. Airlines have postponed their flights for the fear of corona virus. COVID-19 has fetched a marked shift in the lifestyle and economy of Bangladesh. During COVID-19 tourism and hospitality sector is one of those sectors which is mostly affected. Tour abridgement were imputed on all travel destinations, due to the country-wide lockdown, adjourn hotel, motel, and also transportation activities. Earlier, hotels were 80% booked by tourists from our country and abroad. Biman Bangladesh airlines have taken some initiative to reduce their employees including a 10% reduction of basic salaries for all employees and they have also postponed overtime payment as well as they decrease all extra allowances. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic Bangladesh airlines are suffering from huge losses in airline business. Never the less, International Air Transport Association (IATA), have faced a huge loss of income near about USD 252,000,000 from airlines business this year compare to the earlier \$113,000,000 because of the corona pandemic outbreak (Deb & Nafi, 2020). The IATA has projected that world air transit income will be potted by 11% in 2020, which means

a loss of US\$163 billion dollars. During corona pandemic More than two million flights have been postponed till 30 June, 2020. Approximately 65.5 million jobs are associated with the aviation sector, and it can predicted that nearly 25 million aviation-related jobs are at risk globally (Roche, 2020). Passengers, head of Cruise ships were infected coronavirus and also researchers faced a huge challenges to protect patients from corona virus (Del Rio & Malani, 2020). The corona pandemic prevalence is prominent to have hostile impression on the world tourism and hospitality industry. During corona pandemic Chinese tourists lifestyle, choices, preferences and interest are changing for short and long term periods (Wen et al., 2020). This paper point outs the future impacts of corona pandemic in our buying behavior, consumer traits, world connectivity, physical and psychographic and other marketing activities. The consumer behavior have changed for a long-term and also consumer buying patterns shifts in different ways in market (Zwanka & Buff 2020). The main aims of this study is to pursue the influence of the Covid-19 on traveler's behavior and recognize traveler's attitude to remain at home rather than going outside unnecessarily as a result of this pandemic. The outcome reveal that the present novel coronavirus pandemic is prospective to have an influence on tourist behavior in terms of financial expenditures, personal safety, condemnation and attitude (Chebli & Said, 2020). The novel coronavirus is a big challenge at the present situation in the globe. Together with no annotation and no sufficient medical facility, capacity to medicate the coronavirus infected patients, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPI) are the prime stratagem that apprehend the COVID-19 pandemic. Infrequent world travel abridgement as well as the acute command of home quarantine of greater portion of the world are creating a complete breakdown of the world economy since World War II. International tour prohibition has touched 90% of the global population. Eextensive limitation on public assembly and society liveliness are responsible for huge suspension in tourism sector in March, 2020. The researchers surveyed that pandemic situations has impact on our society, economy and tourism (Gössling et al., 2020). Consumer behavior is fluctuated severely in emergency. Consumer food hoarding behavior and their readiness to pay for fresh food to reserves are tremendously increased due to corona pandemic (Wang et al., 2020). COVID-19 has impacts on food supply chain as well as elasticity of supply chain. Food supply chain has faced shortage of labor, breakdown of transportation, communication and customers have also preferred to take foods at home as well as consumers have prioritized at local foods supply chains (Hobbs, 2020). Consumer behavior also shifts in group traveling abridgement due to lack of medical facilities (Yau et al., 2020). The demands of vegetables and fresh foods increased day by day and consumer purchased foods from online shops (Chang & Meyerhoefer, 2020). The service quality is highly varied in terms of buying intentions, service loyalty, retention of customer and word-of-mouth communication (Alexandris et al., 2002). The researchers have analyzed that Environmental, situational and individual factors have effects on tourist behavior and opinion (Pizam et al., 1999). Tourist spot are empty, consumer movement are prevented and also travelling are restricted due to corona pandemic (Bhuiyan et al., 2020). Travel destinations should be restricted for the visitors so that pandemic will not spread in globe (Jamal & Budke, 2020). In this pandemic situation people should aware about corona pandemic and also grown sense of hygiene, sanitation and maintain social distance (Kaushal & Srivastava, 2020). Government has banned transportation, travelling, close borders because of such tourism sectors faced loss like airlines, hotel management and transport agency (Ulak, 2020). Tourism and hospitality sector has enough contribution in any country economy but due to corona pandemic travelers are infected by novel coronavirus that's why it hampered the normal activities of tourism and hospitality sector (Ranasinghe et al., 2020). Due to corona pandemic investment in tourist amenities has changed and tourist

agencies have analysed and identified the profitable areas and tried to adjust this situation (Safaeva, 2020).

1.2 Research Gap

Previous researcher has found that consumer behavior is changed during lockdown, quarantine, fear of disease. These factors have impacts on consumer psychological factors as well as physical factors. But we try to find out the other factors because of consumer behavior is changing due to government rules and regulation, safety and security and social distancing. It also has impacts on consumer income, consumption, visiting tourists spot. People are not visiting the travel destinations because of their health concerns. Government shut down the tourists places due to corona virus. So, Consumer behavior is shifted because they have to use mask in public places due to corona pandemic. Though the articles related to Shifts in consumer behavior due to corona pandemic in tourism and hospitality sector are not available that's why it's difficult to me to find out the factors.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure – 1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Author

1.4 Research Hypothesis

- Ho1: There is no changes of respondent's income in context of corona pandemic
- Ho2: There is no changes of respondent's expenditure on purchasing food from restaurants in context of corona pandemic
- Ho3: There is no changes of respondent's travel expense in context of corona pandemic
- Ho4: There is no changes of respondent's consumption in context of corona pandemic
- Ho5: There is no changes of respondent's mask uses in context of corona pandemic
- Ho6: There is no changes of respondent's visits to amusement parks in context of corona pandemic

- Ho7: There is no changes of respondent's visits to travel destinations in context of corona pandemic
- Ho8: There is no changes of respondent's ordering foods online in context of corona pandemic

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Research Type

This study is a descriptive type of research where quantitative data were collected through survey questionnaire to analyze the shifts in consumer behavior during corona pandemic in tourism and hospitality sector in Bangladesh.

2.2 Source of Information

Two sources of data, primary and secondary data were used in this research paper so that to make the report more meaningful and presentable. The primary data were collected from students, teachers, businessmen, service holders and others via social media and directly by asking question and sharing Google form. The secondary data were collected by reviewing different article literature review. Recently published articles, websites, journals, books and newspapers were very helpful in this regard.

2.3 Questionnaire and scale

A self-administered structured questionnaire was pre-eminently used for assembling the data for this research paper. The questionnaire also covered Ordinal Scale, Nominal Scale and 5 point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree) and some open ended questions. Respondent's age, gender, income and occupation measured through nominal and ordinal scale. Likert scale and open ended question were useful Knowing about how consumer's opinions changes due to corona pandemic.

2.4 Sampling Method

In this research paper non-probability sampling method (convenience sampling technique) is applied. A sample size of 150 individuals were selected from population. These sampling included students, teachers, businessmen, service holders, unemployed and others. we applied convenience sampling method in our study.

Table-1: Sampling design and procedure

Item	Description
Target Population	Tourist, Passengers, Travel agencies, Restaurant's owners and consumers in Dhaka and Cumilla district.
Study Area	Dhaka and Cumilla district
Sampling Technique	Convenience type non-probability sampling
Sample Size	150

2.5 Data Analysis Plan

This research paper has been done by quantitative analysis and in this study all statistical tools such as Descriptive Statistics and Pair-Sample T Test analyzed through SPSS version 23 software tool were used.

3. Data Analysis and Findings

3.1 Respondent's Demographic Characteristics:

In this study total of 150 responses were collected. The mean value of respondent gender, marital status, age, education qualification and occupation were 1.3200, 1.7800, 2.6800, 4.1000 and 3.0000 respectively. Among these, 68% and 32% respondents were from gender group men and women respectively. Marital status were 22% and 78% from married and

unmarried respectively. Among these, 26% and 44% respondents were from age group 21 to 25 and 26 to 30 respectively. The education qualification of the respondents were 18%, 26% and 38% from under graduate, graduate and post-graduate respectively. Among the occupation, 33%, 20% and 18% were from students, teachers and service holders respectively and rest of the percent were businessmen, unemployed and others. The details about respondent's demographic characteristics are given below.

Table- 2: Descriptive Statistics of the respondent's demographic part:

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Gender	150	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.3200	.46804	.219
Marital Status	150	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.7800	.41563	.173
Age	150	4.00	1.00	5.00	2.6800	.88477	.783
Educational Qualification	150	5.00	1.00	6.00	4.1000	1.25719	1.581
Occupation	150	5.00	1.00	6.00	3.0000	1.77227	3.141
Valid N (list wise)	150						

Source: Software output

Table - 3: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Men	102	68.0
Women	48	32.0
Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Married	33	22.0
Unmarried	117	78.0
Age	Frequency	Percent
15 to 20	9	6.0
21 to 25	39	26.0
26 to 30	66	44.0
31 to 35	9	6.0
36 to 40	6	4.0
41 to up	21	14.0
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Secondary School Certificate (SSC)	9	6.0
Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC)	6	4.0
Under Graduate	27	18.0
Graduate	39	26.0
Post-Graduate	57	38.0
PhD	12	8.0
Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Student	45	33.0
Teacher	30	20.0
Businessman	9	6.0
Services Holder	27	18.0
Unemployed	24	16.0
Others	15	10.0
Total	150	100.0

Source: Software output

4.2 Descriptive Statistics on Consumer Behavior During corona Pandemic:

The shifts in consumer behavior is related to the corona pandemic. In this study, 3.70 mean value was found for -visiting tourist place is less attractive during corona pandemic' and 4.0067 for -health conscious people preferring to eat at home during corona pandemic.

Table - 4: Frequency, Percentage and Mean of Shifts in Consumer Behavior during Corona Pandemic:

S,L	Item	F&P	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total	Mean
01	Visiting tourist place	Frequency	15	8	18	75	34	150	3.7000
		Percent	10.0	5.3	12	50	22.7	100	
02	Public vehicles	Frequency	11	17	16	70	36	150	3.6867
		Percent	7.3	11.3	10.7	46.7	24.0	100	
03	Private transport	Frequency	9	27	27	79	8	150	3.3333
		Percent	6.0	18.0	18.0	52.7	5.3	100	
04	Restaurant is safe for food	Frequency	38	44	20	44	4	150	2.5467
		Percent	25.3	29.3	13.3	29.3	2.7	100	
05	People are preferring	Frequency	29	15	17	71	18	150	3.2267
		Percent	19.3	10.0	11.3	47.3	12.0	100	
06	Order food online can be safe	Frequency	12	7	25	74	32	150	3.7133
		Percent	8.0	4.7	16.7	49.3	21.3	100	
07	Health conscious people	Frequency	15	7	4	60	64	150	4.0067
		Percent	10.0	4.7	2.7	40.0	42.7	100	
08	Mask is commonly used in public transport	Frequency	2	17	11	76	44	150	3.9533
		Percent	1.3	11.3	7.3	50.7	29.3	100	
09	Tourist spot is avoided due to different Govt. policies.	Frequency	2	18	15	82	33	150	3.8400
		Percent	1.3	12.0	10.0	54.7	22.0	100	
10	Public transport	Frequency	6	17	26	78	23	150	3.6333
		Percent	4.0	11.3	17.3	52.0	15.3	100	
11	Tourist normally trying to avoid	Frequency	6	14	11	80	39	150	3.8800
		Percent	4.0	9.3	7.3	53.3	26.0	100	
12	The fear of COVID-19 will remain	Frequency	2	19	37	76	16	150	3.5667
		Percent	1.3	12.7	24.7	50.7	10.7	100	

Source: Software output

Restaurant is safe for food during corona pandemic.

Figure-2: Percentage Distribution

29.3% respondents disagreed and agreed that restaurant is safe for foods during corona pandemic, on that issue 13.35% remained neutral, while 2.7% strongly agreed and 25.3% strongly disagreed.

The fear of COVID-19 will remain even the pandemic was over.

Figure-3: Percentage Distribution

50.7% respondents agreed and 10.7% strongly agreed that the fear of COVID-19 will remain even the pandemic was over and 24.7% stayed neutral. 12.7% respondents disagreed and 1.3% strongly disagreed.

3.3 Paired Sample T-Test on Shifts in Consumer Behavior before and during Corona Pandemic:

The dependent t-test (called the paired sample t-test in SPSS Statistics) compares the mean between two related groups on the same continuous, dependent variable. There are four assumptions about paired sample t-test, Assumption-1: Continuous scale used for measuring the dependent variable, Assumption-2: Independent variable must compile of two connected categories, Assumption-3: The deviation between two related groups should not vary significantly & Assumption-4: The difference between two connected categories of dependent variables is approximately normally distributed.

Table- 5: Paired Sample T-Test on the Shifts in Consumer Behavior before and during Corona Pandemic:

Item	Before Corona Pandemic	During Corona Pandemic	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Correlation (r)	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Mean					
Monthly income	15438	8515.5	6922.9	10682.484	.765	7.937	.000
Monthly expense in restaurants	2815.0	1170.4	1644.6	2.995.444	.975	6.724	.000
monthly expense for travel	1704.7	868.00	836.66	1589.644	.536	6.446	.000
Purchase foods from restaurants	11.4133	2.8133	8.600	11.545	.345	9.123	.000
Use mask in public transport	5.5000	23.8600	-18.36	11.264	.125	-19.96	.000
Visit amusement park by bus/airlines	4.7333	1.5000	3.233	4.3108	.795	9.186	.000
visit travel destinations	3.8600	1.5800	2.280	4.337	.459	6.439	.000
Order foods from online	2.8400	3.0467	-.2067	4.097	.437	-.618	.538
Overall Mean & Std. Devi	2498.256	1323.338	1174.963	1538.835			

Source: Software output

Table- 6: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
1. Monthly Income before and during corona pandemic	6922.9	10682.484	872.221	5199.446	8646.487	7.937	149	.000

Source: Software output

To test the hypothesis that before corona pandemic (M = 15438) and during corona pandemic (M = 8515.5), mean different is 6922.9 and $t(149) = 7.937$. Paired Sample T-Test results provide sufficient proof to reject the null hypothesis (Ho1) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic affect the significant changes in consumer income.

Table - 7: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
2. Monthly expense in purchasing foods from restaurants before and during corona pandemic	1644.6	2995.444	244.577	1161.3126	2127.887	6.724	149	.000

Source: Software output

To test the hypothesis that the mean value 2815.0 and 1170.4 for before and during corona pandemic respectively, mean different is 1644.6 and $t(149) = 6.724$ and also there is a significant correlation $r = .975$. Paired Sample T-Test results provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Ho2) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic affect the significant changes in consumer expense in restaurants.

Table - 8: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
3. Monthly expense for traveling before and during corona pandemic.	836.66	1589.64	129.794	580.192	1093.1411	6.446	149	.000

Source: Software output

To test the hypothesis before corona pandemic ($M = 1704.7$) and during corona pandemic ($M = 868.00$), mean different is 836.66 and $t(149) = 6.446$. Paired Sample T-Test results provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_03) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic significant changes in consumer expense for travel.

Table - 9: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
4. Monthly purchase foods from restaurants before and during corona pandemic.	8.6000	11.545	.94255	6.737	10.463	9.123	149	.000

Source: Software output

Paired Sample T-Test results provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_04) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic significantly affects consumer’s foods purchasing from restaurants.

Table - 10: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
5. Monthly use of mask in public transport before and during corona pandemic.	-18.36	11.264	.91970	-20.177	-16.543	19.963	149	.000

Source: Software output

To test the hypothesis that the mean value 5.500 and 23.8600 for before and during corona pandemic respectively, mean difference is -18.36 and $t(149) = -19.963$. Paired Sample T-Test results provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_05) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic significant changes the people use mask in public transport.

Table - 11: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
6. Monthly visit to amusement park by bus/airlines before and during corona pandemic.	3.233	4.311	.35197	2.538	3.929	9.186	149	.000

Source: Software output

Since p value is less than the significant level (.05). So, the null hypothesis (Ho6) is rejected. The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic significant shifts in tourists visit in amusement park by bus/ airlines.

Table – 12: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
7. Monthly visit to travel destinations before and during corona pandemic.	2.280	4.337	.354	1.580	2.980	6.439	149	.000

Source: Software output

To test the hypothesis that the mean value 3.8600 and 1.5800 for before and during corona pandemic respectively, mean different is 2.28000 and $t(149) = 6.439$. Paired Sample T-Test results provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Ho7) since p value is less than the significant level (.05). The rejection of null hypothesis means corona pandemic significant changes the behavior of tourists to visit travel destinations.

Table – 13: Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Sample Test								
	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
8. Monthly order foods from online before and during corona pandemic.	-.2067	4.0967	.33449	-.86762	.45329	-.618	149	.538

Source: Software output

Since p value is more than the significant level (.05) So, the null hypothesis (Ho8) is accepted. The acceptance of null hypothesis means corona pandemic has no significant change in the consumer's foods ordering from online.

4. Discussion

In light of analysis and findings the researcher found that corona pandemic shifts or significantly changes the behavior of consumer in tourism and hospitality in Bangladesh. Due to corona pandemic consumer behavior is changed like tourists are avoiding visiting tourist spots and purchasing foods from restaurants. Due to corona pandemic consumers have maintained lockdown and social separation direction have disordered the consumer normal buying behavior and shopping. Consumers are trying to adjust this new habits (Sheth, 2020). Due to COVID-19 food retail shops and food related service sectors have faced an identical challenges and also consumer want to purchase food staying their home (Goddard, 2020). Now a days, consumers are more health conscious because of they have been involved online foods ordering. 50% people agree that visiting tourist place is less attractive during corona

pandemic and 46.7% people agree that passengers avoided public vehicles for safety and security and also 50.7% agree 29.3% strongly agree that during corona pandemic consumer use mask. Monthly income of consumer mean (15438 and 8515.5 before corona pandemic and during corona pandemic respectively). Monthly expense of consumer mean (2815.0 and 1170.4 before and during COVID-19 respectively). So, due to corona pandemic consumer income is decreased and expenditure is also decreased in tourism and hospitality sector. Consumer's purchasing foods from restaurant is decreased due to corona pandemic but use of mask is increased in public transport. The Mean of consumer's visit frequency before corona pandemic is 3.8600 and during corona pandemic is 1.5800. So, tourist are less visiting to travel destinations during corona pandemic.

5. Conclusion, Recommendations and Limitation

5.1 Conclusion

Above the findings it is clear that COVID-19 shifts the consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality sector. Lockdown, isolations, fear of infection from virus, government rules and regulations changes the consumer income, consumption, use of mask, visit to travel destinations and Amusement Parks. Use of mask, order foods online are seems ever higher than before during corona pandemic. So, there is a huge change of consumer behavior towards above mentioned sector during corona pandemic than before. Health conscious peoples have not visited tourist spot and avoid eating and purchasing food from restaurants. The researchers believe that this study will help the restaurants owners and tourist to understand COVID-19 and how it shifts in consumer behavior.

5.2 Recommendations

The researchers have derived from the analysis part that Corona Pandemic shifts the consumer behavior in tourism and hospitality sector. In light of analysis and findings of this study, the researchers have attained the circumstances where some recommendations for tourism and hospitality sector (hotel, motel, resort, transportation etc.) to adjust the current pandemic situation so that they can provide the better services to consumer. Current study provides few recommendations. First, management of tourism and hospitality sector should focus on those variable, which are changed during corona pandemic. Second, the restaurants management should focus on cleanliness, tidy, environment friendly and hygiene decoration. Lastly, online foods delivery services are highly effective at this pandemic situation, so restaurants management should provide fresh foods, timely delivery to consumer and maintain service quality.

5.3 Limitation of the Study

There are very few limitation we have faced while preparing this research paper. Most significant limitations are- this research topic is new, the articles related to the shifts in consumer behavior due to Corona Pandemic in tourism and hospitality sector were not available, and the convenience sampling is used in this research paper, so biasness may be occurred in our study.

References

- Alexandris, K., Dimitriadis, N., & Markata, D. (2002). Can perceptions of service quality predict behavioral intentions? An exploratory study in the hotel sector in Greece. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*. 12(4), 224-231 Doi: 10.1108/09604520210434839
- Bhuiyan, M. A. H., Hassan, S., Darda, M. A., & Habib, M. W. (2020). Aspects of Sustainable Tourism Development and COVID-19 Pandemic.
- Chang, H. H., & Meyerhoefer, C. (2020). *COVID-19 and the demand for online food shopping services: Empirical evidence from taiwan* (No. w27427). National Bureau of Economic Research.

- Chebli, A., & Said, F. B. (2020). THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON TOURIST CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR: A PERSPECTIVE ARTICLE. *Journal of Tourism Management Research*, 7(2), 196-207.
- Deb, S. K., & Nafi, S. M. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Tourism: Perceptions from Bangladesh. Available at SSRN 3632798.
- Del Rio, C., & Malani, P. N. (2020). COVID-19—new insights on a rapidly changing epidemic. *Jama*, 323(14), 1339-1340.
- Goddard, E. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on food retail and food service in Canada: Preliminary assessment. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue canadienne d'agroeconomie*.
- Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 1-20.
- Hobbs, J. E. (2020). Food supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue canadienne d'agroeconomie*.
- Jamal, T., & Budke, C. (2020). Tourism in a world with pandemics: local-global responsibility and action. *Journal of Tourism Futures*.
- Kaushal, V., & Srivastava, S. (2020). Hospitality and Tourism Industry amid COVID-19 Pandemic: Perspectives on Challenges and Learnings from India. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 102707.
- Pizam, A., Chon, K. S., & Mansfeld, Y. (1999). *Consumer behavior in travel and tourism*. Psychology Press.
- Ranasinghe, R., Damunupola, A., Wijesundara, S., Karunarathna, C., Nawarathna, D., Gamage, S., ... & Idroos, A. A. (2020). Tourism after Corona: Impacts of Covid 19 Pandemic and Way Forward for Tourism, Hotel and Mice Industry in Sri Lanka. *Hotel and Mice Industry in Sri Lanka (April 22, 2020)*.
- Roche, I. (2020). COVID-19 Financial Impact.
- Safaeva, S. (2020). Investment in the tourism sector: the pandemic and its impact. *Архив научных исследований*, (32).
- Sheth, J. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on Consumer Behavior: Will the Old Habits Return or Die?. *Journal of Business Research*.
- Ulak, N. (2020). A Preliminary Study of Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Outbreak: A Pandemic Leading Crisis in Tourism Industry of Nepal. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Education*, 10, 108-131.
- Wang, E., An, N., Gao, Z., Kiprop, E., & Geng, X. (2020). Consumer food stockpiling behavior and willingness to pay for food reserves in COVID-19. *Food Security*, 12(4), 739-747.
- Wen, J., Kozak, M., Yang, S., & Liu, F. (2020). COVID-19: potential effects on Chinese citizens' lifestyle and travel. *Tourism Review*.
- Yau, E. K. B., Ping, N. P. T., Shoesmith, W. D., James, S., Hadi, N. M. N., & Loo, J. L. (2020). The behaviour changes in response to COVID-19 pandemic within Malaysia. *The Malaysian Journal of Medical Sciences: MJMS*, 27(2), 45.
- Zwanka, R. J., & Buff, C. (2020). COVID-19 Generation: A Conceptual Framework of the Consumer Behavioral Shifts to Be Caused by the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 1-10.

Cite this article:

Nishat Nigar & Md. Rukon Miah (2020). Shifts in Consumer Behavior Due to Corona Pandemic: A Case of Tourism and Hospitality Sector in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(12), 123-135. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4282021>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/631.pdf>

Published by

